

INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EUROPE

Between 2016 and 2021 it grew by 57.9%

The Desi Index calculates the value of the Integration of Digital Technology. The variable is composed of three sub-variables in turn constructed through the aggregation of further variables.

Ranking of European countries by value of integration of digital technology in 2021. Finland is in first place by value of integration of digital technology with a value of 14.87 units, followed by Denmark with a value of 14.48 units and from Sweden with a value of 14.08 units. In the middle of the table are Croatia with a value of 9.99, Luxembourg with a value of 9.86 and the Czech Republic with a value of 9.77. Romania closes the ranking with a value of 5.94 units, followed by Hungary with a value of 5.82, and Bulgaria with a value of 5.12 units.

Ranking of European countries by percentage change in the value of integration of digital technology between 2016 and 2021. Latvia is in first place in terms of the percentage change in integration of digital technology with a value of 95.26 equal to a value of 3.27, followed by Estonia with a value equal to 85.53 equal to a value of 4.78 units, and by Italy with a value equal to 79.22 equal to an amount of 4.58 units. In the middle of the table there is Germany with a value equal to 57.74 equal to an amount of 3.25 units, followed by France with a value of 57.28 equal to an amount of 3.17 units, followed by the Czech Republic equal to an amount of 55.76 equal to a value of 3.50 units. Cyprus closes the ranking with a value of 45.22 equal to a value of 2.38 units, Portugal with a value of 38.09 units equal to a value of 2.52 units and Slovakia with a value of 36. , 97.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Using the k-Means clustering algorithm optimized for the Silhouette coefficient, it is possible to obtain a three-cluster structure between European countries for the value of the integration of digital technology. The clusters are shown below:

- Cluster 1: Romania, Hungary, Poland, Latvia, Bulgaria, Greece.
- Cluster 2: Luxembourg, Estonia, Czech Republic, Austria, Croatia, Portugal, Spain, Italy, Germany, France, Lithuania, Slovenia, Slovakia, Cyprus;
- Cluster 3: Sweden, the Netherlands, Denmark, Belgium, Ireland, Finland, Malta.

Considering the value of the median of the clusters, it appears that the countries that have the highest value of integration of digital technology are those of cluster 3-C3 with a value of 12.711, followed by the value of cluster 2-C2 equal to an amount of 9 , 81 and from Cluster 1-C1 equal to a value of 6.204. From a geographical point of view, a distinction is evident between the countries of Northern Europe which have very high levels of integration of digital technologies, compared to the countries of Central-Southern Europe which have intermediate levels, and with the countries of Eastern Europe at the last place. The classic distinction in terms of the ability to implement new technologies between the countries of the North Sea, the countries of continental and southern Europe, and the countries of the East is therefore confirmed.

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Network Analysis using the Manhattan distance. An analysis is presented below through the use of network analysis carried out using the distance to Manhattan. The analysis shows the presence of two complex structures and 5 simplified network structures or consisting of only two nodes. There is a complex network structure between Austria, Luxembourg and the Czech Republic, in particular:

- Austria has a connection with the Czech Republic with a value of 0.08 units and with Luxembourg for a value of 0.15 units.
- Luxembourg has a connection with Austria for a value of 0.16 units, and with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.15 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Austria for a value of 0.08 units and with Luxembourg for a value of 0.15 units.

There is a triangular complex network system consisting of Germany, France and Italy. Particularly:

- Germany has a link with Italy for a value of 0.089, and with France for a value of 0.15 units;
- Italy has a connection with Germany for a value of 0.089 units and with France equal to a value of 0.18 units;
- France has a connection with Germany for a value of 0.15 units and with Italy for an amount of 0.18 units.

There are also five simplified network structures or consisting of a connection between only two countries as indicated below, namely:

- Hungary has a one-to-one connection with Romania equal to an amount of 0.16 units;
- Denmark has a one-to-one connection with Sweden for a value of 0.17;
- Slovakia has a one-to-one connection with Cyprus equal to a value of 0.13;
- Belgium has a one-to-one connection with Ireland equal to a value of 0.068 units.

Conclusions. The value of the integration of digital technologies detected within the DESI index grew by 57.9% on average between 2016 and 2021 for the countries analyzed. The data show that there is certainly a recovery from countries that were backward such as Italy. However, there is a significant dominance of the countries of Northern Europe and in particular of Scandinavia in the integration of digital technologies compared to the areas of continental, southern and Eastern Europe. The network analysis shows that the internal dynamics of the data presents a substantially simplified network structure or constituted at most by groups of three countries. It should be considered that the integration of digital technologies has an impact on the ability of companies to do digital business, to implement e-commerce and help SMEs to increase the efficiency related to new technologies. It therefore follows that to increase productivity and increase the ability of companies to innovate and export it is necessary to grow in the integration of digital technologies. In this regard, public incentives in the context of the economic policies of industry 4.0 can play an essential role in guiding companies to use new technologies, especially in the countries of Southern and Eastern Europe.

Declarations

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